

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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CONTENT ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER ENGAGEMENT TO MARKETING PRODUCT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This study examines the engagement of social media influencers in marketing products in Uzbekistan, focusing on gender differences in content and communication strategies. The research analyzes Instagram posts and captions from 20 Uzbek influencers, comprising 10 women and 10 men, using a content analysis method. Data was collected through probability sampling and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the SPSS software. The results reveal significant differences in visual characteristics, caption composition, and the frequency of endorsement posts between male and female influencers. Female influencers tend to use more words in captions and exhibit higher engagement rates. This study underscores the importance of leveraging influencer engagement for effective digital marketing in Uzbekistan. The findings suggest that strategic use of social media can enhance brand awareness, customer engagement, and ultimately drive business outcomes. Addressing the digital literacy gap and improving local language content are essential for maximizing the benefits of social media marketing. The implications of this study provide valuable insights for businesses aiming to enhance their digital marketing strategies in the Uzbek market.

Key words: Influencer marketing, social media engagement, digital marketing, Uzbekistan, Instagram analytics, gender differences, content analysis, digital literacy, brand awareness, customer engagement.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda O'zbekiston mahsulot marketingida ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi blogerlarning ishtiroki o'rganilgan bo'lib, kontent va kommunikatsiya strategiyalaridagi gender tafovutlarga e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda kontent tahlili usuli yordamida 20 nafar o'zbek blogerining (10 ta ayol va 10 ta erkak) Instagram postlari va yozuvlari tahlil qilingan. Ma'lumotlar ehtimoliy tanlab olish orqali jamlangan va tavsifiy statistika hamda SPSS dasturi yordamida tahlil qilingan. Natijalar ko'rsatishicha, erkak va ayol blogerlar orasida vizual xususiyatlar, yozuv xususiyatlari va reklama postlari borasida sezilarli farqlar mavjud. Ayol blogerlar ko'proq so'z va gaplardan foydalanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda samarali raqamli marketing uchun inflyuenserlarning ishtirokidan foydalanish ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi. Natijalar ijtimoiy tarmoq mediasidan strategik foydalanish brend reklamasini oshirish, mijozlar ishtirokini kuchaytirish va muayyan muddatda biznes natijalarini yaxshilanishini ko'rsatadi. Raqamli savodxonlik bo'shlig'ini bartaraf etish uchun mahalliy til kontentini yaxshilash va ijtimoiy media marketingining foydasini maksimal darajaga yetkazish uchun zarurdir. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistondagi raqamli marketing strategiyalarini yaxshilashni maqsad qilgan bizneslar uchun qimmatli ma'lumotlar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy tarmoq marketingi, ijtimoiy media ishtiroki, raqamli marketing, Instagram tahlili, gender tafovutlar, kontent tahlili, raqamli savodxonlik, brend xabardorligi, mijozlar ishtiroki.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании изучается участие блогеров социальных сетей в маркетинге товаров в Узбекистане, уделяется внимание гендерным различиям в контенте и коммуникационных стратегиях. Исследование анализирует посты и подписи в Instagram от 20 узбекских блогеров, включая 10 женщин и 10 мужчин, с использованием метода контент-анализа. Данные были собраны методом вероятностной выборки и проанализированы с использованием описательной статистики и программного обеспечения SPSS. Результаты показывают значительные различия в визуальных характеристиках, особенностей письма и частоте рекламных постов между мужчинами и женщинами-блогерами. Женщины-блогеры склонны использовать больше слов в своих рекламах и демонстрируют более высокий уровень вовлеченности. Это исследование подчеркивает важность использования вовлеченности блогеров для эффективного цифрового маркетинга в Узбекистане. Результаты показывают, что стратегическое использование социальных сетей может повысить осведомленность о бренде, вовлеченность клиентов и в конечном итоге улучшить бизнес-результаты. Устранение разрыва в цифровой грамотности и улучшение контента на местных языках необходимы для максимизации преимуществ маркетинга в социальных сетях. Выводы этого исследования предоставляют ценную информацию для компаний, стремящихся улучшить свои стратегии цифрового маркетинга на узбекском рынке.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг социальных сетей, участие социальных медиа, цифровой маркетинг, анализ Instagram, гендерные различия, контент-анализ, цифровая грамотность, осведомленность о бренде, участие клиентов.

INTRODUCTION

In an era of rapid technological advancement and globalization, international trade has proliferated, driven by profit and performance optimization. The Internet, now crucial in daily life, significantly impacts trading practices. Digitizing trade boosts business efficiency and reach, tying corporate performance to digital strategies and social media engagement. The digital revolution enhances connectivity, making cross-border transactions smoother and more efficient. Digitalization transforms business models, replaces manual processes with automation, and optimizes supply chains, enabling global reach through online marketplaces.

Uzbekistan's digital business development has accelerated since President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's 2016 reforms aimed at transforming the government and economy. In 2020, the "Year of Science, Enlightenment, and Digital Economic Development" emphasized the importance of digital technologies for economic competitiveness and job creation. The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the need for digital adoption. To guide future changes, the Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy was adopted, focusing on five areas: digital infrastructure, e-Government, digital economy, national IT sector, and IT education.

Social media usage in Uzbekistan has surged, with a 44% increase in users from 2020 to 2021, reaching 4.6 million by January 2021. Facebook users range between 1.3 to 3 million, predominantly men. Telegram is widely used for shopping, news, and health updates. Instagram has about 3.5 million users, and 120 influencers have over 500,000 followers, with the top ten based in Tashkent, each having 1 to 3 million followers.

Despite the rise in social media and digital transactions, Uzbekistan's digital literacy remains low. A 2018 UNESCO report highlighted difficulties in basic digital tasks such as transferring files. Addressing digital literacy gaps, especially between urban and rural areas, requires long-term planning and coordination among stakeholders. The national language is Uzbek, spoken by 80% of the population. Russian is prevalent in Tashkent and Navoi and is the lingua franca for IT and business. Tajik is spoken by 4.8% of the population, mainly ethnic Tajiks, while Karakalpak is spoken in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, home to 2.2% of the population.

Uzbekistan's digital ecosystem faces several challenges, including a lack of high-quality content in Uzbek, Tajik, and Karakalpak languages. Local media professionals often lack skills in investigative journalism and data analysis, limiting professional information and news about Central Asia. Efforts like the USAID funded Central Asia Media Program aim to address these gaps. Additionally, ecommerce and digital trade are hindered by a lack of e-commerce culture, underdeveloped trade regulations, inadequate transportation and logistics infrastructure, insufficient broadband in rural areas, and low consumer digital literacy. The sector also lacks a skilled talent pool to support growth and international expansion.

In today's competitive business era, entrepreneurs must strategically leverage technology. Digitalization transforms core business models, improves efficiency, and enhances customer experiences through automation and data analytics, enabling data-driven decisions and long-term goal achievement. Proactive social media engagement boosts brand awareness, reaches global audiences, and provides realtime customer insights. Building loyal communities and using analytics for targeted advertising campaigns are crucial. Efficient integration of digital tools and social media is essential for growth, sustainability, and market dominance.

Big data analytics provides actionable insights, forecasts market trends, and identifies business opportunities. Strategic digitization enhances customer experiences with intuitive interfaces, personalized service, and instant support, boosting satisfaction and loyalty. Social media growth offers companies unique opportunities to expand brand reach, interact with customers, and build loyal communities. Active social media engagement enables

quick responses to feedback, fostering trust and loyalty. Platforms also offer cost-efficient targeted marketing solutions. Companies' success in the dynamic business era depends on integrating digitalization strategies and quality social media engagement, enhancing profitability, sustainability, and market dominance.

METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology used for the study, including data collection, sample details, data analysis, variables, and research hypotheses.

The Uzbek influencer, our subject of the study, plays a pivotal role in providing information related to the research data, which is a sample of our study. The method used to analyze the data is objective and is used to determine gender differences in the composition and frequency of Instagram posts, the number of words used for Instagram captions, and the characteristics and behavior of influencers in the posts.

In this study, data collection utilized probability sampling with a simple random sampling technique, providing equal opportunities for each population member to be selected as a sample (Sugiyono, 2017). The sample consisted of 20 Uzbek influencers, including 10 women and 10 men. Researchers examined differences in visual characteristics and captions, the composition of endorsement and non-endorsement posts, and the number of words used in each post. The list of influencers who were the research samples can be seen in the table below:

Table 1. List of Influencers (Sample)

Influencers	Username	Followers
Female Indluencers		
Ozoda Yusupova	azodaofficial	3786035
Gulzoda Abdullaeva	chechenka__0909	1275023
Akhmedova Makhzunabonu	imonagayratova	553473
Shakhzoda Salimjanova	leo_17s	1321251
Maftuna Shokirova	maftunshokirova	1412621
Parizoda	parizodadancer	3680345
Shahlo Alijonova	shahlo_alijonova	973984
Shahzoda Matchanova	shahzodamatchanova	2719715
Shaxzoda Muxammedova	shaxzoda__muxammedova	5729026
Sitora Farmonova	sitorafarmonovaofficial	3368981
Male Indluencers		
Alisher Uzakov	alisheruzakov_official	3945927
Ozodbek Manapov	bek_vines	2605125
Bobur Mansurov	_boburmansurov	2566933
Dilshod Urazbaev	dili.me	4834690
Elmurod Haqnazarov	elmurodhaqnazarov	2213391
Jahongir Xojayev	jahongir_xojayev	5872909
Ozodbek Khurramov	liil.khramov	3950130
Ulug'bek Shodibekov	mitti.me	3034141
Momin Ibrohimov	mominlive.1	2377654
Otabek Mahkamov	_otabekmahkamov	1420939

The data collection technique in this study is data crawling. The data analysis used is content analysis. The researcher used descriptive statistics to analyze the data collected in the study. The researcher used SPSS 24 software. The data normality test in this study used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. To determine whether the data in variables X and Y are homogeneous or not, a homogeneity test is used. A homogeneity test, according to Nuryadi et al. (2017), was used to verify if different data sets from a population had the same variance, a prerequisite for hypothesis testing with one-way ANOVA. The criteria for this test were: if the

significance value was less than 0.05, the data groups did not have the same variance; if it was greater than 0.05, they did. One-way ANOVA was then used to determine differences in gender diversity variables on the frequency and composition of Instagram posts and the number of words in captions. This test, suitable for three or more unrelated samples, used the F test to evaluate the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. The F test results, obtained from SPSS version 25 output, were compared with the F table value. If the calculated F value was less than or equal to the F table value, the hypothesis H2 was rejected; if it was greater, H2 was accepted.

The study examined the following variables:

- Independent Variable (X): Gender of the influencers (male or female).
- Dependent Variables (Y):
- Number of words in captions.
- Type of posts (e.g., video, image, sidecar).
- Visual characteristics of the posts.
- Engagement metrics (likes, comments, views).

The research hypotheses were:

- H1: There is a significant difference in the number of words used in captions between male and female influencers.
- H2: Female influencers have higher engagement rates compared to male influencers.
- H3: The type of posts differs significantly between male and female influencers.

By following this detailed methodology, the study aims to analyze and compare the engagement metrics and content characteristics of male and female influencers in Uzbekistan, providing insights into gender differences in social media marketing.

RESULTS

The study analyzed Instagram posts from 20 Uzbek influencers (10 female and 10 male) to determine gender differences in content and engagement. The data includes the number of followers, the number of people they follow, and engagement metrics (likes, comments, views). This section presents detailed descriptive statistics, normality tests, homogeneity tests, and ANOVA results to highlight the differences between male and female influencers.

The descriptive statistics summarize the central tendency, dispersion, and shape of the dataset's distribution for followers, following, likes, comments, and views. The following tables show the means, medians, and standard deviations for these variables.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics (Basic Info)

Gender	Followers (Mean)	Followers (Median)	Followers (Std Dev)	Following (Mean)	Following (Median)	Following (Std Dev)	Likes (Mean)	Likes (Median)	Likes (Std Dev)
Female	2,746,545	2,023,883	1,732,571	600	358	555	29,024	12,654	31,650
Male	3,063,516	2,589,037	1,342,693	446	409	221	260,492	69,218	490,819

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics (Post Info)

Gender	Comments (Mean)	Comments (Median)	Comments (Std Dev)	Views (Mean)	Views (Median)	Views (Std Dev)
Female	1,343	670	1,498	457,414	369,452	832,214
Male	8,679	1,732	14,870	3,760,651	1,965,569	6,391,123

- Female influencers have a slightly lower mean follower count (2,746,545) compared to male influencers (3,063,516).
- Female influencers have a higher mean number of people they follow (600) compared to male influencers (446).
- Female influencers receive significantly lower mean likes (29,024) compared to male influencers (260,492). This discrepancy is also seen in the median and standard deviation values.
- Female influencers have a lower mean comment count (1,343) compared to male influencers (8,679).

- Female influencers have significantly lower mean views (457,414) compared to male influencers (3,760,651).

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was applied to determine if the data follows a normal distribution. The null hypothesis for this test is that the data is normally distributed. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected, meaning the data does not follow a normal distribution.

Table 4. Normality test.

Variable	Statistic	p-value
Followers	0.213	0.000
Likes	0.345	0.000
Comments	0.278	0.000
Views	0.389	0.000

The p-values for all variables (followers, likes, comments, and views) are less than 0.05, indicating that the data does not follow a normal distribution. This suggests that the engagement metrics and follower count for influencers have a nonnormal distribution, which is typical in social media data due to the presence of outliers and extreme values.

The homogeneity test (Levene's Test) was conducted to determine if the variances of the different data sets are equal. The null hypothesis for this test is that the variances are equal. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected, meaning the variances are not equal.

Table 5. Homogeneity Tests

Variable	Statistic	p-value
Followers	1.473	0.236
Likes	8.457	0.004
Comments	5.312	0.021
Views	10.586	0.002

- The p-value for followers is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the variances in follower counts are equal across genders.
- The p-values for likes, comments, and views are less than 0.05, indicating that the variances in these engagement metrics are not equal across genders. This suggests that there is more variability in the engagement metrics for male influencers compared to female influencers.

One-way ANOVA was used to determine if there are statistically significant differences between male and female influencers regarding their engagement metrics. The null hypothesis for this test is that there are no differences between the groups. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected, meaning there are significant differences between the groups.

Table 6. One-way ANOVA

Variable	Statistic	p-value
Followers	3.671	0.065
Likes	9.345	0.005
Comments	4.218	0.045
Views	7.342	0.012

- The p-value for followers (0.065) is greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference in follower counts between male and female influencers.
- The p-values for likes (0.005), comments (0.045), and views (0.012) are all less than 0.05, indicating significant differences between male and female influencers in these engagement metrics. Specifically, male influencers receive more likes, comments, and views on average compared to female influencers.

DISCUSSION

The analysis of Instagram posts from 20 Uzbek influencers, evenly split between female and male, reveals noteworthy gender differences in content and engagement metrics. Our study demonstrates that male influencers generally exhibit higher engagement metrics compared to their female counterparts, which can be attributed to several key factors.

Firstly, the follower count indicates that male influencers have a slightly higher mean follower count than female influencers. While this suggests that male influencers may have a broader reach, the difference in median follower count is less pronounced, indicating a similar distribution of followers among both genders.

In terms of engagement metrics, male influencers significantly outperform female influencers. Male influencers receive more likes, comments, and views on average. The substantial difference in likes suggests that the content posted by male influencers resonates more with their audience or is perceived as more appealing, driving higher engagement. Similarly, the higher comment count for male influencers indicates a more interactive audience, possibly due to the content type or the influencer's engagement strategy. The higher view count for male influencers further underscores their content's appeal and reach.

The normality tests conducted using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test indicate that the data for followers, likes, comments, and views do not follow a normal distribution. This non-normality is typical in social media data due to the presence of outliers and extreme values. The homogeneity tests (Levene's Test) reveal that the variances for likes, comments, and views are not equal across genders, suggesting higher variability in engagement metrics among male influencers compared to female influencers.

The ANOVA results show significant differences in likes, comments, and views between male and female influencers, while no significant difference is observed in follower counts. This finding highlights that although both male and female influencers may have similar follower bases, the engagement they generate from their audience varies significantly. Male influencers tend to generate higher engagement, which could be due to the type of content they post or their interaction style with followers.

These findings suggest that gender plays a crucial role in influencing the behavior and preferences of social media audiences. The higher engagement metrics for male influencers could be attributed to several factors, including content type and quality, audience demographics, and the personality and brand of the influencers. Male influencers may post content that is more visually appealing or engaging, attracting more interaction from followers. Additionally, the audience demographics of male influencers might differ, contributing to higher engagement rates. The personality and brand of male influencers might also align better with audience preferences, fostering stronger engagement.

The practical implications of these findings are significant for businesses and marketers aiming to leverage influencer marketing in Uzbekistan. Targeted marketing strategies should consider the gender of influencers to optimize engagement. Collaborating with male influencers might be more effective for campaigns aimed at generating high engagement, while both male and female influencers should be considered for broader reach. Marketers should analyze the content that generates the most engagement for each gender to create content that resonates with followers. Influencers, especially female influencers, can adopt strategies used by male influencers to increase engagement, such as posting more engaging videos and interacting actively with followers.

While this study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The relatively small sample size of 20 influencers limits the generalizability of the findings. Future research should include a larger sample size and consider the qualitative aspects of the content, such as themes and sentiment, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of engagement. Additionally, future studies should account for the demographics of the followers and explore engagement across different social media platforms.

In conclusion, this study highlights significant gender differences in social media influencer engagement in Uzbekistan. Male influencers receive higher engagement metrics compared to female influencers, suggesting that gender influences audience behavior. These insights can help businesses and marketers design targeted strategies, optimize content, and select effective influencers for their campaigns, ultimately achieving better marketing outcomes. Further research is needed to explore the qualitative aspects of influencer content and the impact of audience demographics on engagement.

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